

COVID19 DRUG REVIEW DISCUSSIONS

Subjects: Medicinal Chemistry | Virology

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Definition

In this type of note some probable drugs both the antiviral as well as non- antiviral synthetic drugs including vaccines development serving against Covid19 commonly used under trial basis are taken into discussion .Starting from Hydroxy-Chloroquine sulphate to Remdesivir just some points are discussed only but the in detail study regarding Structure , SAR , Q -SAR ,Formulations Pharmacology / Bio-logical activities are available in the following BIBLIOGRAPHIC discussions .Remdesivir is highlighted in image since it is only effective drug against SARS-COV-2 in presence or in absence of interferon 1b .The term " Drugs " broadly classified to synthetic drugs as well as vaccines under trial .

1. Hydroxy Chloroquine – Sulphate– In generic use although Chloroquine is used as antimalarial but the Hydroxy-Chloroquine Sulphate can also be used to reduce the inflammation during the attack of Covid19 . Initially although the Drug was not getting approval from WHO but later on the drug is approved by WHO .
2. Lopinavir – Ritonavir Combination (antiviral)– This combination is used against HIV in the treatment of AIDS can be used against Covid infection crucially .But most efficient anti-viral against Covid19 – Remdesivir & Probably the final solution.This drug is specific to severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS-COV-2) .
3. Favipiravir (antiviral) –This drug is used against the treatment of Japanese influenza is also used in India under the approval of DGCA , Govt of India , and Glen mark Pharmaceuticals Ltd . This drug is a cheaper one than Remdesivir itself . It can be also used in diabetic & Hypertension patients of Covid19 .
4. Rimantadine (Amantadine) – This drug is under trial but found efficient for elderly patient to treat respiratory syndrome due to Covid19 .
5. Dexamethasone – A non anti-viral cortico-steroid used as life saving medicine (LSM) during severe Covid19 infection . But it is non covid specific and also having other broad spectrum uses .
- 6 . Interferon – Beta – 1b – used for symptomatic Covid infections in combination with best Lopinavir – Ritonavir to Remdesivir if necessary.
- 7 .**Remdesivir - The most effective antiviral against SARS-COV-2 used in wide spectrum in severe acute respiratory failure .**

REF : asbmd.org

The second portion of the discussion contains **vaccine development** .

The vaccine development including trial has already started SII (Pune) are under trial of Phase2-3 trials . AstraZeneca - Oxford university , Cansino , Pfizer are trying under trial vaccine . As we are all aware that it is a long way to find out the ethical trial (clinical efficacy) universally U.S.S.R has been under claim stage of Sputnik V final phase trial . We the common people are in good hope that the vaccination will get in success to stop such Spike Crown .Without the term immunity vaccination will not be effective to eradicate the viral infection .!

Vaccine development under trial -1. AZD1222-A decision is taken by the panel of expert of AZ Pharma will review the unexpected of UK patents

-<https://health.economicstimes.indiatimes.com/tag/unexplained+illness> For Immunity booster

-new formulation based on Zinc Gluconate and natural Vitamin C coming from Acerola Cherry for boosting immunity -To accelerate vaccine work<https://health.economictimes.indiatimes.com/tag/covid-19+drug>.

2. Covid19 Vaccine is totally unpredictedhttps://health.economictimes.indiatimes.com/l.php?url=https%3A%2F%2Fhealth.economictimes.indiatimes.com%2Fnews%2Findustry%2Ftaking-the-good-with-the-bad-how-potential-covid-19vaccines-offered-hope-and-disappointment%2F78069594&mailer_id=0&item_id=3919885&dt=2020-09-12&utm_source=Mailer&utm_medium=ET_batch&utm_campaign=ethealth_news_2020-09-12

3. A venture of Serum Institute of India<https://health.economictimes.indiatimes.com/tag/serum+institute+of+india>

4. Whether Mask is an equivalent Vaccine -<https://www.webmd.com/lung/news/20200909/couldyour-mask-be-a-kind-of-vaccine-against-covid-19>

5. CPT(Convalescent plasma therapy) -Not effective to reduce the mortality of severe Covid-infection<https://www.webmd.com/lung/news/20200909/could-your-mask-be-a-kind-of-vaccine-against-covid-19> Variolation "of SARS-COV-2 -Waiting for a vaccine - 10.1056/NEJMp2026913

6. Immunological response of Covid Vaccination -SARS , MERS Epidemic .

7. Article Immune responses in COVID-19 and potential vaccines: Lessons. Activated Vit-D for better Immunity .

8. Military Growing policy through vaccine research in China<https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-020-02523-x> .

9. Chemist Martin Brooke has developed a unique test of Covid for students of Illinois University but the infection of the Spike protein can't be stopped -<https://www.npr.org/sections/healthshots/2020/08/15/902616040/can-testing-students-for-coronavirus-twice-a-week-prevent-campus-outbreaks> .

10 . Please look back on Gam-COVID-Vac <https://www.raps.org/news-and-articles/newsarticles/2020/3/covid-19-vaccine-tracker>

11. The third trials of AZ resumes trial in U.K-<https://www.hindustantimes.com/worldnews/suspension-of-astrazeneca-covid-19-vaccine-trials-showed-fallacy-of-approach-rd-if-ceo/story-rw09PX3WZQAKo1onyT6WEL.html>

12. COVISHIELD trial -<https://www.timesnownews.com/health/article/covishield-update-oxford-covid-19-vaccine-likely-to-be-the->

13 . SPUTNIK- V - This vaccine has already claimed Post registration clinical trial of SPUTNIK V for 40,000 people in Russia and Belarus has been successfully administered without any complications -<https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/show/NCT04437875?term=Gamaleya&draw=2&rank=2> .

14. Social consciousness to be developed for better lifestyle more immune to us against viral attack or antibody generation . Immunity is surely correlated for vaccination or immunological biotechnology of SARS-COV-2 infection . The above discussion links are

showing a great effort of a potent Covid -vaccination with **appropriate clinical safety and efficiency trial**

REFERENCES :

1. https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Jaydip_Datta/questions -

(**Datta J , Shall we believe that the Covid19 has a asymmetric characteristics of Malaria and Crown virus ? , May 01 , 2020 .**

2. **Datta J , Justification of Lopinavir - Ritonavir & Finally Remdesivir (higher generation of acyclovir analog) used in Covid19 treatment ? , May 13 , 2020 .**

3. **Datta J , Flavipiravir - Justification of use against Covid19 ? June 21 , 2020 .**

4. **Datta J , Broad Spectrum Synthetic Antiviral Compounds (Including covid19) - A Short Review ? , June ,30 ,2020**

5. https://www.researchgate.net/post/Whether_Chemistry_Pharmacy_are_interdisciplinary-acedemics_research-updated_to_pandemic_Covid19 -Jaydip Datta ,2020.

6

.https://www.researchgate.net/post/What_is_fate_of_Clinical_Ethics_in_case_of_Final_trial_of_a_New_Drug - Jaydip Datta , 2019 .

7. Covid19 , Covid19 : IMMUNITY AND LIFESTYLE - Datta Jaydip -

(<https://encyclopedia.pub/item/revision/a69b9fb73d328ace21eb6e2858b29d63>)

9 **Datta J , researchgate.net (RG)**

9.1) *Do We believe that spreading & death of people by Covid 19 is due to severe damage of Environmental Sustainability ?*

(Started April 7) .

9.2) *How Drugless therapy helps us to Improve our health as well as to prevent Viral attack ?(Started February 28) .*

9.3) *Shall we believe that the Covid19 has a asymmetric characteristics of Malaria and Crown virus ? (Started May 1) . What is Malnutrition - Do You agree it is a Global Problem particularly in the Third world countries ? (Asked December 11,2019) .*

9.4) *What is GREEN HEALTH ? (Asked December 1, 2019) .*

9.5) *What is Food adulteration - Is it a Big Problem ? (Asked November 11 , 2019) What is balanced diet - Will You support that it is essential to fight against COVID-19 ? (Asked November 7 , 2019) .*

9.6) *What do you prefer to take ANIMAL or VEGETABLE protein under attack of corona virus ? (Asked October 28 , 2019) . Mental Frustration during LOCKDOWN period of Covid19 is more prone towards infection Share your feelings ? (Asked December 19 , 2019) .*

9.7) *What is SLEEP ? (Asked October 9 , 2019) Your favourite food as Anti-Oxidant - Let us discuss ? (Started September 27 , 2019) TEA or COFFEE - Which one is good for health ? (Started October , 29 , 2019) .*

10. **HEALTH & ENVIRONMENT: A SOCIOLOGICAL CONCIIOUSNESS (Preprint) ,researchgate.net (RG) -Datta J . November 2019.**

11. **BALANCED DIET & ADULTERATION : An Impression (Experimental Findings) ,**

researchgate.net (RG)-Datta J, ebruary 2020 .

12. Nature@newsletter.nature.com.

13. newsletter@ethealthworld.com.

14. [https://www.researchgate.net/post/Covid19 Vaccination-How far How long](https://www.researchgate.net/post/Covid19_Vaccination-How_far_How_long) - Datta Jaydip .

15. [https://www.researchgate.net/post/What is fate of Clinical Ethics in case of Final trial of a New Drug](https://www.researchgate.net/post/What_is_fate_of_Clinical_Ethics_in_case_of_Final_trial_of_a_New_Drug) -

Datta Jaydip .

16. [https://www.researchgate.net/post/Whether Bio-Technological Research is essential to](https://www.researchgate.net/post/Whether_Bio-Technological_Research_is_essential_to_develope_our_na-)

[develope our na-](https://www.researchgate.net/post/Whether_Bio-Technological_Research_is_essential_to_develope_our_na-)

[tion including the threats of Corona Virus-How](https://www.researchgate.net/post/Whether_Bio-Technological_Research_is_essential_to_develope_our_na-) - Datta Jaydip .

17. [https://www.researchgate.net/post/Let us Discuss something about Reproducible](https://www.researchgate.net/post/Let_us_Discuss_something_about_Reproducible_research_technique_in-)

[research technique in-](https://www.researchgate.net/post/Let_us_Discuss_something_about_Reproducible_research_technique_in-)

[cluding COVID 19](https://www.researchgate.net/post/Let_us_Discuss_something_about_Reproducible_research_technique_in-) - Datta Jaydip .

18. [https://www.researchgate.net/post/What is our Knowledge or Updates about Covid19-It](https://www.researchgate.net/post/What_is_our_Knowledge_or_Updates_about_Covid19-Its_source_devel-)

[s source devel-](https://www.researchgate.net/post/What_is_our_Knowledge_or_Updates_about_Covid19-Its_source_devel-)

[opement measurement](https://www.researchgate.net/post/What_is_our_Knowledge_or_Updates_about_Covid19-Its_source_devel-) - Datta Jaydip.

19. Covid19 Vaccine development (?) { News updatate (Preprint article) , Datta Jaydip ,

figshare.con , Sept ,2020

20.

[https://www.researchgate.net/post/What is fate of Clinical Ethics in case of Final trial of a New Drug](https://www.researchgate.net/post/What_is_fate_of_Clinical_Ethics_in_case_of_Final_trial_of_a_New_Drug) , Jaydip Datta.

Keywords

Covid19;SARS-COV-2;Respiratory Syndrome;Antimalarial;Lopinavir-Ritonavir;Remdesivir;Interferon-Beta-1b;Dexamethasone;Vaccine development;Clinical trial

Retrieved from <https://encyclopedia.pub/1988>